

1 **ICP27 protein of HSV-1 is oncogenic.**

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6 We measured total transcription in cells with doxycycline-inducible gene expression to study the
7 transcriptional control by the HSV-1 gene product ICP27. We present evidence here for oncogenic-type
8 properties of HSV-1 ICP27. ICP27 activated the small oncogene *TCTA*, the oncogenic homeobox *Hoxc6*
9 and the Hox cluster non-coding RNA *HOTTIP*. ICP27 activated *Tbx3* and ILF3-DT. ICP27 activated APC
10 beta-catenin pathway tumor suppression indicated by induction of *Arvcf*.

11 Citations

12 1. Sandri-Goldin, R.M., 1998. ICP27 mediates HSV RNA export by shuttling through a leucine-rich
13 nuclear export signal and binding viral intronless RNAs through an RGG motif. *Genes & development*,
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